

ISSUES OF FORMATION OF LEGISLATION IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, WHICH WILL RADICALLY IMPROVE THE ACTIVITIES OF THE LEGAL SERVICE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6645964>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022

Accepted: 02nd June 2022

Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

Legal service, legal adviser, rule of law, individuals and legal entities, government agencies

ABSTRACT

This article describes in detail the development of legislation on legal services, its system and structure, legal status, the main directions of legal services in public and economic administration, local government and a number of other topics. features and areas of activity of the legal service are analyzed.

It is known that our state, which fulfills the legal, social and economic tasks of ensuring the independence of our national development in all respects, is carrying out reforms in the field of civil and property relations based on the principles of international law.

The legal service plays an important role in building a strong rule of law in our country, achieving the rule of law and justice. With the help of the legal service, the legal awareness and culture of citizens will be raised, and the rule of law will be ensured in the activities of public authorities and businesses. [1]

Over the past period, the country has taken comprehensive measures to ensure the rule of law and the rule of law in the activities of state bodies, economic

management bodies, state enterprises, institutions and organizations (hereinafter - the state bodies and organizations).

Compliance with the law is facilitated by the rule of law of government agencies and organizations, the legal services that carry out contractual and litigation work.

At the same time, the work of legal services does not yield the expected results due to the fact that they do not have sufficient and effective powers to prevent violations of the law and take timely action on them.

The order of organization of legal services, the lack of criteria for determining their staffing units do not allow to ensure a reasonable definition of the organizational staffing structure of legal services in

various government agencies and organizations.

The work of legal services to study and generalize law enforcement practices, to develop proposals for improving the legislation is not effectively organized. Work in this area is limited to taking measures to eliminate shortcomings and violations identified by law enforcement and regulatory agencies.

The level of funding of legal services staff hinders the involvement of highly qualified personnel with higher legal education and general experience in the field, which has an impact on the quality of legal services.

[3]

The Decree of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated October 21, 2016 "On measures to further reform the judicial system, strengthen guarantees of reliable protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens" set the task to further improve and increase the efficiency of legal services in government agencies. As part of the implementation of the decree, the resolution "On measures to radically improve the activities of the legal service," signed by the President on 19 January this year, was an important step in this direction. [4]

When it comes to legal services, many people think of a lawyer who works only for formalities. In fact, the person in this position should be a well-educated, open-minded, up-to-date specialist in charge of ensuring the rule of law.

Indeed, in our country, which has chosen the path of building a democratic state based on the rule of law, the rule of law and the rule of law are the main principles. To this end, our country has undergone radical reforms in recent years, and this process is continuing. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev

has set specific tasks for us to ensure the rule of law in society. There is a need to improve the legal service, as it is an important link in achieving this goal.

Although legal services have been the normative, contractual, and litigation work of government agencies and organizations, their efforts to prevent violations and take timely action have been inadequate. This was due to the fact that they did not have sufficient and effective powers. It's no secret that some leaders have chosen to act without a lawyer or have tried to persuade a lawyer to do so.

Some ministries and agencies have passed a number of legal documents and thousands of employees, but only one or two legal positions have been introduced. In fact, some of them do not have these services at all in their regional offices.

The focus on reforming the sector has shown the high level of the President's confidence and attention to the legal service, as well as to lawyers. It is no exaggeration to say that the decision was an important document that will take the legal service to a new level.

One of the most important aspects of this decision is that, in addition to enhancing the status of the legal service and strengthening social protection, it also expanded the scope of its responsibilities to ensure the rule of law, and strengthened the responsibility and accountability. The long-awaited issues in the field have been fully resolved.

The resolution now establishes a procedure for the mandatory establishment of legal services in government agencies and organizations, including their territorial structures, in accordance with the minimum norms and criteria established by the Cabinet of

Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Reductions in staffing of this service are not allowed.

Another problem is that staff shortages in this area have hampered the training of senior legal staff. Lack of protection and lack of prospects for workers in the industry would lead to their transfer to other industries. In particular, the procedure for the self-employment or dismissal of legal service personnel by the head of the organization has led to some restrictions on their legitimacy activities.

Now, in accordance with the established procedure, such cases have been completely eliminated. Employees of the legal services of state bodies and organizations will be appointed and dismissed on a mandatory basis in coordination with the Ministry of Justice. In addition, the judiciary has been given the right to initiate disciplinary proceedings against the heads of state bodies and organizations that violate the requirements of the legislation governing the activities of the legal service.

The new procedure provides a solid basis for legal staff to carry out their duties within the law. Allows the judiciary to guarantee them.

Another important rule has been set to attract young professionals to the industry and increase its attractiveness. According to him, employees of the legal service will also be given the same ranks as employees of the judiciary, and the procedure for payment of bonuses for many years of service will be applied.

Most importantly, when an employee joins other government agencies, including law enforcement and oversight bodies, his or her length of service as a legal service employee is taken into account, as well as

his or her length of service to pay for many years of service.

Employees of legal services of state bodies and organizations with three years of experience in this specialty have the right to participate in the qualifying examination as a candidate for a license without passing the relevant internship to become a lawyer.

All of the above will undoubtedly increase the interest of qualified professionals in this field. In turn, there is an opportunity to select qualified personnel for the industry. This will serve to increase the quality of activities in the industry.

The head of our state has always stressed the importance of "taking measures to prevent the problem, not to deal with its consequences." These views are fully reflected in the decision. In particular, the legal services are obliged to take compulsory measures to resolve disputes arising with the participation of their organizations. The establishment of mandatory submission of draft orders, decrees, contracts and other documents of a legal nature to the legal service for legal examination is also a procedure aimed at preventing violations.

In addition, the mandatory legal opinion of public authorities on decisions affecting the exercise of the rights and freedoms of individuals and legal entities has been strengthened. This norm provides for the legal assessment of documents adopted by government agencies, their "filtering" before execution.

The decision assigned another important task to the legal service. As you know, 2017 has been declared the Year of Dialogue with the People and Human Interests in our country. A qualitatively new system of dealing with appeals of

individuals and legal entities has been introduced.

Based on this, the resolution stipulates that the decisions of state bodies and organizations, as well as complaints about the actions or inactions of their officials must be considered by the legal services of state bodies and organizations.

The legal service must perform the functions assigned to it by law in a necessary and effective manner. Immediately notify the higher body, the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other law enforcement agencies of violations of the law in the state body and organization, as well as in the structures of its system need to give.

The full implementation of such responsibilities in the legal service will ensure the rule of law.

The Ministry of Justice has been designated as a specially authorized body for coordination and methodological support of legal services, attestation and training of its staff. For this purpose, the relevant departments are being established

in the Ministry's Department for Coordination and Methodological Support of Legal Services, the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent city justice departments. Necessary measures are being taken to fill the department with qualified personnel with experience in working with the legal services of government agencies and organizations, who will be able to perform the tasks assigned to them at a high level. [3]

The Ministry is conducting the necessary advocacy activities to inform the heads of government agencies and organizations and legal services about the content of this decision. The capital also hosted an international conference on "Current issues of further improvement and development of legal services in government agencies and organizations." Such events are organized in all regions of the country.

In short, the radical improvement of legal services on the basis of this decision will help them to work effectively and ensure the rule of law in our country.

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